

FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES WITH NON FRACTURING

REINFORCING ELEMENTS.

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The reinforcing elements used in fibrous composites can be arranged not to fracture under overstrain conditions by means of a stress controlled reversible decoupling mechanism operating at the fibre matrix interface. By this means decoupling is initiated at the centre of a long fibre and progresses outwards as the tensile load increases. In this way a fibre of any length can be pulled through the composite structure at high stress levels against frictional losses. This mechanism adds to the existing reinforcing principle the following features (a) a fail safe mechanism (b) very considerable energy absorbing capabilities and (c) crack stopping characteristics. The design and experimental properties of composites based on these principles are outlined.

Introduction.

The reinforcement of a relatively soft and extensible matrix by a reinforcing phase comprising strong, stiff, lightweight reinforcing elements, having themselves very small failing strains, is the fundamental concept upon which almost the whole of the research carried out to date on fibrous composites has been based. Compared with ductile metals such composites have a fundamental limitation in their very low failing strains which are in the region of 1%. This follows from the low failing strains of the reinforcing elements and the fixed characteristics of the fibre/matrix interface. In general, these low failing strains have been accepted as inevitable and attention has been focussed on ways by which the rupture strengths and works of fracture of fibrous composite systems might be improved.

The reinforcing principle can be preserved, and fibre fracture also prevented, if the fibre matrix interface is made active in the sense that its properties are changed locally, by the local tensile stresses carried by the reinforcing element. In particular the local shear strength of the fibre matrix interface has to be made to fall as the local tensile stress carried by the reinforcing element increases (1). In the simplest case this can occur in a linear fashion so that

$$\tau_{\sigma} = \tau_0 (1 - \sigma/\sigma_{\max}) \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where τ_{σ} is the shear strength of the fibre matrix interface when the local fibre tensile stress is σ , τ_0 is the shear strength of the fibre matrix interface when the tensile stress carried by the fibre is zero, σ_{\max} is some upper limiting fibre tensile stress such that $\sigma_{\max} < \sigma_{\text{ult}}$ the fibre breaking stress, and σ is the local stress carried by the fibre. It follows that the stress distribution along a cylindrical fibre of this type, having a diameter $2r$, as it is being withdrawn from the composite structure, is given by

$$\sigma_x = \sigma_{\max} \{ 1 - \exp (- 2\tau_0 x/\sigma_{\max} r) \} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

where x is the distance measured from the free end of the fibre. The shear strength of the fibre matrix interface at the corresponding position is given by

$$\tau_x = \tau_0 \exp (- 2\tau_0 x/\sigma_{\max} r) \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

The mechanism of stress transfer between the composite matrix and a reinforcing element with a stress responsive interface of this type, is compared with that of a conventional composite in which the shear strength of the interface is assumed constant in figure 1.

Various reinforcement stress levels are considered. In the conventional system the stress transfer length at the end of the fibre increases linearly with increasing fibre tensile stress and the central regions of the fibre carry the same strain as that generally prevailing in the composite structure. When the stress transfer length becomes half the fibre critical length, fracture of a long fibre occurs. In the system with the stress responsive interface, the central regions of the reinforcing fibre again carry the same strain as that prevailing in the rest of the composite structure but the stress transfer length now increases exponentially as the general tensile stress carried by the composite is increased. The stress transfer length becomes infinitely large, when the fibre is infinitely long, and carries its maximum limiting stress σ at its centre. The system is self adjusting in that a fibre of any length is always less than the effective critical length, provided $\sigma_{\max} < \sigma_{\text{ult}}$. Under these conditions fracture of a fibre of uniform strength cannot occur. If the stress transfer across the interface takes place by frictional forces, continued tensile extension causes the reinforcing elements to be pulled through the composite structure against frictional losses at stress levels given by Equation 2 where x represents the minimum length of reinforcing element embedded in the composite structure.

Experimental Non-Fracturing Reinforcing Elements.

Two part, core sheath (Duplex) reinforcing elements in which the core has non fracturing characteristics have been manufactured. These have consisted of a narrow bore (hypodermic) steel tube with a steel wire core (2) (3). The wire has a slight helical convolution with a helix angle greater than 80° and with a diameter when unstressed, greater than the internal diameter of the tube. (figure 2). When the wire is inside the tube there is thus a pressure exerted along the line of contact and hence a frictional force resisting displacement of the wire within the tube. As the load carried by the core wire increases the pressure it exerts on the wall of the tube is diminished and the shear strength of the frictional interface is correspondingly reduced. A simple analysis of the situation indicates that, as the tensile load carried by the core increases, complete debonding will occur when the diameter of the helix is reduced to that of the internal diameter of the tube. A change in the curvature of the wire forming the helix, (and hence the helix angle α and also the helix diameter), is produced by the couple $Lr \sin \alpha$, where L is the tensile load applied to the helix and r is the distance between the axis of the helix and the centre of the wire forming the helix. Neglecting torsion and shear effects, because of the very large helix angles, the debonding load L_{\max} is given by (3),

$$L_{\max} = \frac{EI}{r_2 \sin \alpha_2} \left[\frac{\cos^2 \alpha_1}{r_1} - \frac{\cos^2 \alpha_2}{r_2} \right] \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

Where r_1 and r_2 are the distances between the axis of the helix and the centre of the wire when respectively outside and inside the tube and α_1 and α_2 are the corresponding helix angles. E and I are respectively the Youngs modulus and cross sectional geometrical moment of inertia of the wire.

Equation 4 has been observed to be in good agreement with experimental data over a wide range of geometrical conditions but some effects have been noted which are not predicted by the simple theory (4). For example, the diameter of the helix at the fully debonded condition can be measurably less than the internal diameter of the tube. This seems likely to be due to the absorption of energy by frictional losses through differential movements between the core and sheath during the debonding process. Consequently an excessive tensile load has to be applied to the helix to cause it to fully debond and this manifests itself as a reduced helix diameter after debonding. It is important to note that the longitudinal stiffness of the core sheath system, before debonding, is normally similar to the "rule of mixtures" stiffness of the tube plus the wire in the straight condition. Although the stiffness of the free helix would be something like one half of the stiffness of a straight length of similar wire (depending on the helix angle) the stiffness of the combined system, with the wire inside the tube, is enhanced by the very large hoop tensile stresses in the tube and corresponding radial compressive stresses in the helix. This behaviour is examined in more detail elsewhere (5), but is similar to the effect of a mismatch in the Poissons ratio between fibres and matrix in a conventional composite (6). The magnitude of this effect with the core/tube system is, however, very much greater since the effective Poissons ratio of the helical core is an order of magnitude greater than that of a conventional elastic solid. In this way the longitudinal stiffness of the two part (duplex) element in the unbonded condition is controllable by the geometry of the system as well as by the elastic modulus of the component parts.

The frictional shear stress transfer is not affected by conventional lubricants because the contact pressures in the experimental systems studied are greater than the film strengths of these materials. The high contact pressures also lead to relatively high interfacial shear strengths, even for steel on steel, and the consequent effective stress transfer lengths are in the region of 10cms for core elements of about 1mm in diameter. The stress distributions along the core elements have been

observed to correspond quite closely with the stress distribution predicted by Equation 2 under both an applied tensile and compressive load (3). Reinforcing elements, in the size so far investigated, are directly applicable to engineering structures of the order of one metre or greater in longitudinal dimensions. It will be noted that Duplex reinforcing elements, of the type discussed here, can be manufactured in principle from other materials since their operation depends solely on elastic deformations. The helical core elements could, for example, be manufactured from resin bonded carbon or glass fibres instead of steel wire. Also the geometrical form of the system does not necessarily have to be of the type described here. Similar behaviour has been observed with sinusoidally crimped core wires in tubes and for crimped steel strip operating between parallel flat surfaces (3).

Engineering Applications of Duplex Reinforcing Fibres.

Duplex non fracturing fibres reinforce a matrix in just the same way as conventional reinforcing fibres at the engineering design stresses for the structure. In the present experimental systems the cross sectional areas of the core and tube are approximately equal and, as discussed above, the longitudinal stiffness can be controlled by the geometry of the reinforcing element. The use of two separate reinforcing phases, operating sensibly independently of each other, confers some potential advantages in that the tube elements and outer interfaces can be utilised to reinforce a matrix under longitudinal shear and transverse tensile loading - while the core elements and the inner interface provide toughness during transverse crack propagation. This approach avoids the compromise of an interface of intermediate bond strength which is necessary with conventional composites utilising a single type of interface. This aspect of Duplex fibres is discussed in more detail elsewhere (1).

However, the primary advantages of Duplex non fracturing fibres concern the properties they confer to a structural material when subjected to local or general overload conditions. There are few engineering situations in which these issues can be ignored. As the core reinforcing elements do not fail they can continue to carry a tensile stress, as indicated by Equation 2, despite the local fracture of the rest of the composite structure. In stress rupture situations, core element stress levels as high as 130Kg/mm^2 (4) have been observed for elastic systems and σ_{max} values as high as 200Kg/mm^2 have been observed for steel core elements in which the debonding process involved some plastic deformation of the wire (3). Very high composite tensile deformation stresses are thus available coupled with very large tensile elongations, as very long reinforcing elements are pulled through the composite structure against frictional losses. Large amounts

of mechanical energy can thus be absorbed, and the conflict between high yield strengths and large elongations to failure, which is fundamental to metal alloy development, is avoided. When consideration is given to an extensive engineering structure subjected to localised loading, it is clear that the energy absorbing capabilities of duplex fibre reinforced composites can be many times greater than those of ductile metals. This is because the deformation process is not confined, as it is with a metal, to the regions of high stress concentrations. The controlled decoupling of the core/sheath interface provides a stress diffusing capability which, by core fibre "pull through" can cause the whole of the structure to take part in the deformation process. (7) (8) (9).

The Fracture Mechanics of Sheet Metal Reinforced by Non Fracturing Duplex Elements.

Duplex reinforced sheet metal structures offer the combination of sheet metal fabrication technology, the stiffening and strengthening principle of reinforcement, the fail safe characteristics of duplex elements and, because of interactions between the non fracturing reinforcing elements and the rest of the composite structures, an envelope of conditions inside which unstable crack growth in the metal sheet is not energetically possible. Preliminary studies have been made of the mechanics of crack growth in these materials (10) (11) (12) (13).

Two conditions have been investigated (a) the propagation of an edge crack by a crack opening force applied to the mouth of the crack, and (b) the fracture mechanics of a crack in the centre of a semi infinite plate subjected to uniform edge loading under fixed grip conditions. In the first case a contribution to the work of fracture is made by the crack bridging core elements as they are pulled through the composite structure with increasing separation of the crack faces. For a uniform distribution of reinforcing elements the work done is proportional to the area between the crack faces and, therefore, for a crack of triangular shape, it increases linearly with increasing crack length. For narrow triangular cracks (length fifty times the width at the mouth), and a few centimetres long, the contribution to the work of fracture of laboratory non fracturing reinforcing elements (calculated on a weight for weight basis), becomes much greater than that of duralumin (12). The reinforcing elements, of course, continue to carry their limiting debonding load across the crack faces.

For case (b), a theoretical model describing the stress distributions around a crack bridged by non fracturing reinforcing elements has been set up, and the rate of release of strain energy with increasing crack length has been calculated from it (12).

For cracks which are long compared with the plastic zone around the crack tip the rate of release of strain energy dW/da for an unreinforced plate increases linearly with increasing crack length. Figure 3. For the reinforced case, when the core reinforcing elements are capable of carrying the full load applied to the sheet and do not therefore reach their decoupling stress, the rate of release of strain energy tends to some limiting value with increasing crack length. This is because the reinforcing elements limit the elastic relaxation of the metal plate and absorb additional strain energy in the vicinity of the crack. They thus provide a strain energy locking mechanism which becomes more powerful as the crack length increases. Providing the limiting rate of release of strain energy is less than the work of fracture of the metal plate, unstable crack growth is not energetically possible. The general predictions of the simple initial theory have been confirmed (13) and the additional effects of frictional losses associated with differential movement between the core elements and the rest of the composite structure have been calculated, and shown to be of major significance.

Because of the very powerful crack stopping mechanisms associated with non fracturing fibres the very high works of fracture currently necessary to give long critical crack lengths in sheet aluminium structures are no longer necessary. This condition is achievable with relatively low volume fractions (20%) of existing laboratory reinforcing elements (12). It becomes possible, therefore, to add carbon or boron fibre reinforcements with their relatively low works of fracture to the composite engineering structure and still maintain its crack insensitivity. These possibilities are discussed in detail elsewhere (13).

Although the work described here relates to metal sheet structures it is clearly applicable to other engineering components such as hollow tubular driving shafts.

Preliminary observations have now been made of crack growth in duplex reinforced metal sheets under fatigue loading conditions which are otherwise similar to condition (a) described above. Element fatigue lives in excess of 10^6 cycles at peak core stress values of $\sim 50\text{Kg/mm}^2$ have been observed to date without observable fretting damage. The rate of growth of a fatigue crack is, of course, dramatically reduced compared with the unreinforced condition (14). This work is continuing.

Conclusions.

It has been shown to be quite feasible to produce strong brittle but non fracturing reinforcing elements which, at engineering design stresses, stiffen and strengthen a composite structure in just the same way as conventional reinforcing elements. The

stress controlled decoupling process which prevents their fracture also makes them completely insensitive to cracks or other forms of stress concentration and provides a strain diffusing mechanism which causes the whole of the primary reinforcing phase to take part in deformation process. Within a defined envelope of conditions, unstable crack growth is not energetically possible in such composite systems. The approach would seem to be applicable to engineering situations where there is a premium on light weight, fail safe materials. Typical possible applications are aircraft structures generally and helicopters in particular.

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References.

1. Morley J.G. "The design of fibrous composites having improved mechanical properties", Proc. Roy. Soc. Lond. A. 319, 117-126, (1970).
2. Morley J.G. "Fibrous composites with multiple and variable shear strength interfaces", Composites, IPC Science and Technology Press Ltd., Vol. 2, No. 2, 80-84, (1971).
3. Morley, J.G. and Millman, R.S. "The application of self adjusting interfaces to the design of fibrous composites", J. Mater. Sci. 9, 1171-1182, (1974).
4. Chappell M.J., Martin, A. and Morley, J.G. "Characteristics of helical cored non fracturing reinforcing elements", to be published.
5. Morley, J.G., Millman, R.S. and Martin, A. to be published.
6. Hill, R. J. Mech. Phys. Solids, 12, 199, (1964).
7. Morley, J.G. "Call for reinforcements", Chemistry in Britain, Vol. 10, No. 12, 478-482, (1974).
8. Morley, J.G. and Chappell, M.J. to be published.
9. Millman, R.S. and Morley, J.G. to be published.
10. Morley, J.G. "Transverse crack propagation in fibre reinforced composites", Faraday Special Discussions of the Chemical Society, No. 2, 109-116, (1972).

11. Morley, J.G. "New types of energy absorbing processes occurring during crack propagation in complex composites", Proc. of The Third International Conference on the Strength of Metals and Alloys, Vol. 1, 232-236, (1973).
12. Morley, J.G. and McColl, I.R. "The influence of non fracturing reinforcing elements on crack propagation in metal sheets", to be published, J. Phys. D. (1975).
13. McColl, I.R. and Morley, J.G. "Fail safe composite sheets reinforced by non fracturing fibres", to be published, (1975).
14. McColl, I.R. and Morley, J.G. "Preliminary fatigue studies of sheet metal reinforced with duplex non fracturing fibres", to be published.

Figure 1. Stress distributions along fibres having constant shear strength ----- and stress controlled shear strength interfaces ——— .

Figure 2. Section of core sheath (Duplex) reinforcing elements.

Figure 3. Rate of release of strain energy with increasing crack length for a thin metal sheet unreinforced ----- and reinforced with duplex fibres ——— .